

USING MODERN TECHNOLOGIES TO IMPROVE SPEAKING SKILL

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Abstract: Speaking is an essential tool for communicating. In the classroom, improving the speaking abilities of students has always been a concern. In the fast developing 21st century various innovative technologies are being introduced to teach speaking skill in the classrooms. Technology is the vehicle to get access with this modernized world. More than the process of communication, trade and transactions, today technology is widely used in educational sectors.

Keywords: Modern technologies, Internet, communicative skill, method. However, today's world requires that the goal of teaching speaking should improve students' communicative skills, because, only in that way, students can express themselves and learn how to follow the social and cultural rules appropriate in each communicative circumstance. In the preliminary stage, teachers used tape recorders as a technological device to instruct the students, which later evolved as communication laboratory. The integration of technology into language teaching which was started in the early 1960s and 1970s, assisted teachers to teach second language learners how to speak in the best way possible. Every day teachers are getting access to some new technologies, which join hand with English teaching. As the conventional teaching method such as the chalk and talk method seems to be outdated, the modern technologies can be used as a supplement to the classroom teaching method to have a lively atmosphere in the classroom. New technologies in language learning by multiple intelligence and mixed abilities replace with old methods of teaching.

Technology can stimulate the playfulness of learners and immerse them in a variety of scenarios. Technology gives learners a chance to engage in self-directed actions, opportunities for self-paced interactions, privacy, and a safe environment in which errors get corrected and specific feedback is given. Feedback by a machine offers additional value by its ability to track mistakes and link the student immediately to exercises that focus on specific errors. When

links are provided to locate explanations, additional help, and reference, the value of technology is further augmented.

Modern technologies available in education today are: Communication lab, Speech recognition software, Internet, TELL (Technology Enhanced Language Learning), Pod casting, Quick Link Pen, Quicktionary. Communication labs are available to develop speaking skills. By incorporating suitable software through computers the students will play it again and again with their own interest and try to improve their speaking skills, which are most essential in this modernized IT world [3, p.473]. The usage of headphones in the lab makes the students to have interest over the subject and induces them to repeat again and again instead of feeling boredom. Speech recognition software also helps improving the students speaking, this can convert spoken words to machine-readable input. The device recognizes the accuracy of what was read and then provides a positive reinforcement like “You sound great!” or gives the user an opportunity to try again, in this way the learner can figure if he is reading well or not. As the user’s skill improves, the technology reads less material so that the learner reads more. This software also evaluates and provides scores of grammar, pronunciation, comprehension and provided with the correct forms, for examples if a student mispronounces a word, the learning tool can immediately spot it and help correct it. Internet is a commonly acknowledged term and widely used by people throughout the world. Students now use Internet in the class to learn English. Online teaching inside the classroom seems to be interesting and makes the students to find out the suitable materials for them. Internet is a commonly acknowledged term and widely used by people throughout the world. Students now use Internet in the class to learn English. Online teaching inside the classroom seems to be interesting and makes the students to find out the suitable materials for them [4, p. 281]. TELL is the use of computer technology including hardware, software and the internet to enhance teaching and learning of languages. It allows the students to get access with all the technologies available for the enhancement of English learning. Students are allowed to use online dictionaries, chat, and to view the various happenings around the world. Podcasts can be uploaded or downloaded, this audio help the learner familiarize with the target language and teachers can use them as useful audio material that can be used in class for activities like discussions, besides, in the web. Podcast undoubtedly

help learners in speaking. Pod casting is the integration of audio files where we can feed our own materials and ply it inside and outside of the classroom. Students use ipods to hear their favorite music files. In the same way they have their education in the form of entertainment. Podcasting allows students to use their tech-based entertainment systems for educational purposes. Using technology in learning English language has become a real necessity nowadays. This paper has reviewed briefly how technology can be utilized in developing the speaking skill of the learners. Different methods for using technology in improving speaking skill were discussed thoroughly.

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